

Representation Learning of Patient States

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Bowen Fan

Machine Learning and Computational Biology Lab
Department of Biosystems Science and Engineering
ETH Zurich

Introduction

Patient and disease states are usually recorded as digital measurements in electronic health records (EHR), such as vital signs, examination reports, lab measurements, demographics, and also genomics and proteomics profiles. All the information can be transformed into appropriate data representations that can be available for downstream medical machine learning tasks, such as clinical outcome prediction, patients phenotyping, and diagnosis support. However, raw EHRs could be challenging to deal with due to their high dimensionality, irregular temporality, systematic bias and random errors [1]. Therefore, there is a strong need of developing more advanced representation learning methods to tackle these tasks.

In traditional clinical settings, patient states derivation is heavily depending clinical domain knowledge to curate meaningful features. For example, those commonly used clinical scoring models to define patient health states, like KDIGO (Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes) [2] score for prediction of acute kidney injury (AKI) and SOFA (Sequential Organ Failure Assessment) [3] score to evaluate patient organ system failure. Although such expert curated scores have certain advantages like high interpretability and light computation cost, they cannot be generalized to other tasks and might not capture hidden patterns and new knowledge inside the clinical data, thus usually outperformed by more advanced representation learning methods on specific tasks.

To be specific, a good representation learning method should not only help downstream machine learning models to obtain good performance but also achieve reliability and interpretability, with the potential to discover hidden patterns and new knowledge, of which the cause and effect can be determined. Exemplified by some recent studies: an unsupervised multivariate clustering method with radial domain folding algorithm [4] can extract high-level information of the patient states and patient physiology from EHR, and transform them into a dense representation with domain expertise, which can be applied to train a model that outperforms traditional scoring systems on the patient mortality prediction task. A good representation method [5] can also be employed to handle raw data with multimodalities (i.e., data contains both static variables like demographics, and continuous variables like vitals, labs as well as clinical notes) and transform them for downstream clinical intervention tasks.

Development of such representation learning methods have gained a better understanding of patient health states and been utilized to investigate the intersection of machine learning and medical applications, especially building early warning systems to make continuous risk prediction for certain diseases onset. In this deliverable, the general steps to define patient states from EHR and its application on two different diseases early warning system development is introduced, and a new approach to learn meaningful latent representation using hidden Markov model (HMM).

Methods

The very first step is to define appropriate outcome labels, which should only collect data from admission till the timestamp that the alarm is triggered retrospectively, in order to prevent any information leakage beyond the target timepoint. The resolution of the timepoints (i.e., the frequency to make prediction) should be decided based on the granularity of the dataset, which could range from a few minutes to days in different clinical tasks. And the prediction horizon also needs to be defined based on clinical interests, for example, for acute disease like respiratory failure prediction in intensive care units, for which quick interventions are necessary, the warning system looks as short as 8 hours ahead [6]. While for sub-acute decision task like mortality prediction in general wards, much longer horizons (15 days to 90 days) are usually considered [7].

After properly defining the target (both outcome and lookahead), the next, which is also the core step, would be doing feature engineering on the raw data to extract more meaningful features to represent the patient states, as feature engineering is proven to be crucial to machine learning models by making the data compatible with and the machine learning model and improving the performance. Generally, there are four processes should be considered when doing feature engineering.

Feature selection: this involves picking relevant features from a large clinical dataset which may contains thousands of features like MIMIC-III [8] and eICU [9]. This would make the model computation and further analysis much more feasible than feeding all features to the model altogether. For this step, seeking input from clinicians and informaticians familiar with the dataset and the target outcome to select which features to use is essential.

Feature imputation: for most routinely collected EHR, missing of measurement is very common. Different causes of missingness may introduce unintentional

biases to the dataset. For instances, if a lab test is only issued based on a clinician's observation of the patient, whether or not the test is issued provides insight into the patient's status [10], or some measurements were only taken when the patient was admitted to ICU. There are numerous ways to impute the missing data, including filling with mean/median, clinical normal values, forward filling, as well as more advanced multivariate imputation methods like multiple imputation by chained equation [11] and autoencoder (AE) [10].

Feature construction: this is to develop new features apart from the ones already exists in the dataset. Many different strategies could be taken to build new features and cannot be fully covered in this essay, here I will just introduce a few of them that are usually considered in clinical tasks.

- (1) Aggregate temporal information, including both historical and future information. For historical information, we can extract the count, mean, median, standard deviation, difference, trends and so on among subsequent measurements, for a subset of important features. For future information, we can try to regress the feature values in future measurements using regression models like linear regression, elastic net and Gaussian process. For score-based outcome definition, the endpoint of each timestamp is usually derived from current measurements. Therefore, the future measurement could be very helpful if they were accurately regressed.
- (2) Encode missingness indicator. Using binary indicators of features will enable the machine learning model differentiate an imputed value and a real measurement, because we consider the missing data contains valuable information of clinical behaviors as suggested in the feature imputation part.
- (3) Extract hidden features. Besides the above-mentioned approaches, we could also derive some other features via more complex methods to further improve the performance of the prediction model. For example, using principal component analysis (PCA), Gaussian mixture model (GMM) and autoencoder (AE) to learn a latent representation of patient states, such latent features can be used as additional features to the final prediction model and have been verified to be helpful [12].

In a similar manner, we also proposed a new strategy to find latent patterns using HMM, as we assume that HMM could capture the underlying health state which cannot be observed in the EHR. To be specific, the outcome endpoints can be treated as the observable components and the true health conditions of the patient can be considered as hidden components, which could be some high-level conceptions (e.g., a patient being generally good or very sick). As the health condition may change over time when given proper treatment or the disease exacerbate, the observed endpoints would also change along with it, which instantiated as the transition of hidden states and the different observation probabilities correspond to the hidden states in HMM. The transition probabilities between each two hidden states and the observation probabilities for each observation and corresponding hidden state can be acquired using expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm. By extrapolating the transition probabilities and observation probabilities along the timestamps, we could acquire a multinomial distribution of the observations (i.e., the endpoints) at each time step. Subsequently, for a binary target, the predictions can be made by taking the maximum over the prediction horizon. The predictions can be used for baseline comparison as well as additional features to the main model as HMM due to its simple and unsupervised characteristic.

Besides the vanilla HMM, we have also implemented other variants of HMM to introduce more complexity, like the hidden semi-Markov model (HSMM) [13] which except that the underlying process of the is not Markov but semi-Markov. The key difference between HSMM and HMM is that in HMM the hidden state at time t depends exclusively on hidden state at time $t-1$, in HSMM the probability of transition of state j to state k at time t depends not only on the previous hidden state S_{t-1} , but also on the time duration spent in state j

$$P(S_t = k | S_{t-1} = j) = P(S_t = k | S_{t-1} = j, d_t(j)) \quad (1)$$

where the $d_t(j)$ is the amount of time (e.g., the number of timestamps in state j) as the hidden state being j .

another example is using input-output HMM (IOHMM) [14] in which the transition probabilities are directly modulated by external inputs, and these inputs could be some closely relevant measurements.

$$P(S_t = k | S_{t-1} = j, u_t) = \frac{\exp(\log(P_{j,k}) + w_k^T u_t)}{\sum_{k'=1}^K \exp(\log(P_{j,k'}) + w_{k'}^T u_t)} \quad (2)$$

where the transition probability from state j at timepoint $t-1$ to state k at timepoint t $P_{j,k}$ is modulated by the external input u_t , and corresponding weight w_k applied on it. This is designed to mimic the clinicians when they preliminarily evaluate the patients looking at a few critical variables in the first place.

Feature transformation: the last step before feeding all available features to the model to train, including normalization of the numeric features (including capping the outliers), one-hot encode the categorical features and sparse encoding and so on. These strategies might help to improve convergence and also speed up the training. But they are also model-dependent, for example, normalization is very important to most deep learning models while random forests model is known to be much less sensitive to the scales of the input features. After transformation, the sequential data needs to be vectorized in to a feature vector appropriate for model input at each timestamp for model training and prediction.

Further steps in the prediction workflow, such as model training, parameter tuning, metric selection for evaluation and post-hoc results analysis, are beyond the scope of this essay and are not be covered.

Discussion

We are currently running the introduced representation learning methods to define patient states specifically under in the context of two fatal diseases prediction, namely acute kidney injury (AKI) and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS).

Acute Kidney Injury

AKI is a sudden episode of kidney failure or kidney damage caused by the accumulation of waste products in the blood which is hard for kidney to handle

and keep balance of the fluid in the body. The golden standard of defining AKI states is given by KDIGO [15] calculated with patient's serum creatinine level and urine output. AKI states are categorized into three levels according to the severity of the condition (i.e., level 1, 2, 3, while level 0 means no AKI). Unlike kidney failure that results from kidney damage which gets worse slowly, AKI is often reversible if it is detected in time and intervention is given quickly [16]. Therefore, many studies have been done to investigate the possibility of using machine learning approaches for early prediction of AKI under various clinical settings in order to assist clinicians with early treatment [17, 18]. Our works is mainly focusing on AKI prediction in the ICU patients with a prediction horizon of 48 hours.

Multiple Organ Dysfunction Syndrome

MODS is defined as two or more organ systems fail to function properly at the same time, the pathophysiology of MODS is characterized by a severe, systemic, uncontrolled inflammatory process that leads to multiple organ system dysfunctions [19]. It is a severe condition and comes with very high mortality and morbidity. In clinical practice, a patient with no organ dysfunction or single organ dysfunction is usually reversible when proper treatment is given before MODS happens. Our work investigates the sepsis-induced MODS in pediatric sepsis patients and has a focus on the early recognition of the transition from a child who may solely require antibiotics, to a septic child progressing to MODS.

Both works will be submitted for peer review in the future.

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